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A STUDY OF PERCEIVED QUALITY OF WORK LIFE AMONG EMPLOYEES WORKING IN DIFFERENT UNIVERSITIES OF BIHAR STATE, INDIA

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Abstract

The present study was aimed to see the significance of difference between teaching and non-teaching employees working in different universities of Bihar in their extent of perceived Quality of Work Life. For this investigation, two hundred and fifty (N=250) employees comprising Teaching (n=125) and Non-teaching (n=125) were randomly selected from different departments of universities of Bihar and its constituent colleges such as L.N. Mithila University, Darbhanga, B. R. A, Bihar University, Muzaffarpur, Patna University, Patna and B. N. Mandal University, Madhepura. Having collected the data through questionnaire schedules, the data were given statistical treatment, which indicated that there is significance of difference between Teaching and Non-teaching employees, although both the group have indicated favourable inclination towards their Quality of Work Life. It is interesting to note that teaching employees were found more prone to their degree of perceived Quality of Work Life than Non-teaching employees. The findings have been discussed in detail by highlighting the probable reasons.

Key Words: *Quality of Work Life, teaching and non-teaching employees, Bihar*

Introduction:

If we trace back the history of human behavior we find the fact that human beings are continuously engaged since long by putting their all efforts to understand the behavior of people at work and similarly it can be observed that transfer of knowledge is being well equipped for the promotion of different organizations especially our learning organizations. Thus, Quality of Work Life plays a pivotal role in any organization. Simply, QWL is associated with human

resources which are important elements at work that can not be overlooked at any stage of working life. It is undoubtedly fact that the activity of an individual employee is greatly influenced by the elements of Quality of Work Life. People join organizations in their capacities to satisfy their economic, social and psychological needs. Thus, a good Quality of Work Life of any organization is of utmost value in improving an employee's working situations, their skills, attitudes and performance at large.

Quality of Work Life is a set of belief / philosophy, a set of principles, which holds that people are the most important resource in the organization as they are trustworthy, responsible and capable of making valuable contribution on their respective organization, so they should be treated with greater dignity and full respect (Straw et. al., 1984). The elements, those are relevant to an individual's Quality of Work Life include the task, the physical work environment, social environment within the organization, administrative system and relationship between life on and off the job (Cunningham et al., 1990). It is also important to be mentioned that Quality of Work Life consists of opportunities for active involvement in group working arrangements or problem solving that are of mutual benefit to employees or employees which is directly based on employees management relationship. Employee also start to experience of Quality of Work Life as a set of methods such as autonomous work groups, job enrichment, and high level job involvement aimed at boosting the satisfaction and productivity of workers (Feuer, 1989), whereas, Walton(1975) said that it requires employee commitment to the organization and an environment in which this commitment can flourish.

The main objective of Quality of Work Life has been viewed changing with the passage of time. It started with objective of improving wage and working conditions. And thereafter, other strategies like job enlargement and job enrichment emerged for improving employee's motivation and their efficiency. Employees are the backbone of any organization. So, a good Quality of Work Life is required for a healthy mind and sound body, fair working methods, high efficiency of employees on one hand and production and profit on the other as Shamir et al., (1985) viewed Quality of Work Life as a comprehensive construct that includes an individual's job related well-being and the extent to which work experiences are rewarding, fulfilling and devoid of stress and other negative personal consequences.

In addition to above mentioned text, it is important to be mentioned that the term Quality of Work Life has different meanings to different people. Some level it as a happiness program, others especially trade unions name it as a subtle employee incentive or just another productivity device. In the present fast changing scenario of human life Quality of Work Life has assumed increasing interest and importance in both industrialized as well as developing countries of the world. In India, its scope seems broader than much labor legislation enacted to protect the workers. It is more than a sheer work organization movement which focuses on job security and economic growth to the employees. Hence, Quality of Work Life refers to the level of happiness or dissatisfaction with one's career. Those who enjoy their careers are said to have a high Quality of Work Life, while those who are unhappy or whose needs are otherwise unfilled are said to have a low Quality of Work Life.

Recently, the term Quality of Work Life has been defined as 'better job and more balanced ways of combining work life with personal life' (Eurofound, 2006). As the concept of Quality of Work Life is multidimensional, it may not, of course, be universal. However, key concept tends to include job security, reward systems pay and opportunity for growth among other factors (Rossie et al., 2006).

Objective of the present study :

Having scanned the review of literature on the phenomenon, it has been observed that Quality of Work Life of employees has been widely studied (Lawler, 1968; Seashore & Barnowe, 1972; Flangers et al., 1974; Pierce and Danham, 1976; Davis, 1971; Bell, 1974; Jhonson, 1975 and Chaudhary and Ahmad, 2015) and is still has a greater focus on increasingly far more and more humanizing the job conditions as well as the total work environment from different angles. In fact, the present era which is generally assumed as the 'era of stresses', Quality of Work Life strategies are with the fast pace of technological development are dominating the work culture for enhancing individual working efficiency as well as organizational effectiveness. Thus, employee's Quality of Work Life seems to be highly important because satisfaction of employees is basically a back-bone for organizational survival and growth. Hence, by looking at the facts, the present piece of research work was undertaken to

study the perceived Quality of Work Life with particular reference to Teaching and Non-teaching employees working in different universities of Bihar, India and it is still an unexplored area. Thus, the present study will fill the void of knowledge in the area concerned.

Hypotheses:

On the basis of the objectives of the study the following hypotheses were formulated:

- Teaching employees working in different universities of Bihar are likely to be more prone towards the degree of perceived life satisfaction than the group of Non-teaching employees.
- There will be no significant difference between the group of Teaching and Non-teaching employees of Bihar universities in terms of their degree of perceived Quality of Work Life.

METHODOLOGY:

SAMPLE:

In the present inquiry total sample consisted of two hundred fifty (N=250) working employees which were randomly selected from different Universities of Bihar such as L.N. Mithila University, Darbhanga, B. R. A. Bihar University, Muzaffarpur, B.N. Mandal University, Madhepura and Patna University, Patna and its constituent colleges located in urban areas, which comprises the group of Teaching staffs (n=125) and Non-teaching staffs (n=125). In this enquiry subjects' age ranged between 35 – 62 years.

TOOLS USED:

Following tools were used for collecting the data:

- **Quality of Work Life:** For measuring Quality of Work Life (QWL), a scale developed by Shawkat and Ansari (2001) was administered individually to each

respondent of the sample. The QWL scale assess overall numerous dimensions such as work itself, employees' participation, physical working conditions, union-management relations, organizational commitment, supervisory relations, clarity at organization, recognition, economic benefits, self-respect, employee health and Promotion. The scale consisted of 48 items and each item was rated on a 5-point Likert type scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree (1-5). High score indicates high Quality of Work Life and low score indicates low level of Quality of Work life. The split-half reliability coefficient was found to be $r=.70$ and the validity of this scale was found to be $r = .89$ which is also highly significant and confirms the efficacy of the scale.

- **Biographical Information Blank (BIB):** For interpreting the obtained results a biographical information blank was prepared. It includes qualification, age, marital status, religion, sex, number of dependents, experience in the present position, salary and family income etc.

PROCEDURE:

Above-mentioned two materials in printed form were administered individually on the sample to obtain the data and during data collection subjects were assured that the information provided by them on each items of the scale will be kept strictly confidential and will be used for research purposes only.

Having obtained the data on each of the items of the scale, the data were tabulated according to norms and procedures for giving statistical treatment to test the hypothesis formulated. Finally the obtained results were presented in the tables and discussed logically to draw the conclusions.

RESULTS:

TABLE – 1

Table showing comparative levels of perceived Quality of Work Life between Teaching and Non-Teaching Working Employees in the Universities of Bihar State

Levels	Teaching Staffs		Non-teaching Staffs	
	n=125	Percentage	n=125	Percentage
High	74	59.2	62	49.6
Moderate	38	30.4	46	36.8
Low	13	10.4	17	13.6

Mean value = 196.73

Mean value = 177.25

Table - 1 highlights the percentages of Teaching and Non-teaching staffs working in different universities in Bihar such as L.N. Mithila University, Darbhanga, B.R. A. Bihar University, Muzaffarpur, B. N. Mandal University, Madhepura and Patna University, Patna, from where the present study has been carried out with regard to their reactions to the perceived Quality of Work Life. It is evident from the table that 59.2 percent of teaching staffs have indicated higher degree of perceived Quality of Work Life in comparison to non-teaching group of employees who reported only 49.6 percent. While 30.4 percent of teaching staffs working in different universities in Bihar have reported moderate level of perceived reactions to Quality of Work Life, 36.8 percent of non-teaching group have reported moderate level of Quality of Work Life which is comparatively higher when compared to teaching employees i.e. 30.4%. Moreover, 13.6 percent of non-teaching group indicated low level of perceived Quality of Work Life in comparison to teaching employees i.e. 10.4 percent only. Table – 1 also indicates that teaching staffs in comparison to non-teaching staffs working in different universities of Bihar have higher degree of Quality of Work Life as the Mean value of teaching group ($\bar{x}=196.73$ with $SD = 28.75$) is more higher than that of the non-teaching group i.e. $\bar{x}=177.25$ with $SD= 20.38$. Hence, the proposed hypothesis i.e. teaching staffs working in

different universities of Bihar State are likely to be more prone towards perceived Quality of Work Life than Non-Teaching employees group, stands accepted. Above mentioned results can also be observed by the pie chart as illustrated below:

Pie Chart Showing Comparative Levels of Perceived Reactions on

Quality of Work Life among Teaching and Non-Teaching

Employees Working in Different Universities of Bihar, India

Legend indicates Levels: 1 for High, 2 for Moderate, 3 for Low

TABLE – 2: Table showing significance of difference between two groups on their degree of perceived reactions towards Quality of Work Life

Group	n	Mean	S.D.	t	p
Teaching Staffs	125	196.73	28.75	6.15*	0.01
Non-teaching	125	177.25	20.38		

* Indicates significant at 0.01 level.

Table-2 depicts the clear cut picture regarding the significance of difference between the teaching group of staffs and non-teaching group of staffs in terms of their degree of perceived Quality of Work Life as t-value 6.15 has been found highly significant statistically at 0.01 level of confidence. Hence, the proposed hypothesis that there will be no significance of difference between the group of teaching and non-teaching employees working in different universities of Bihar State, India stands rejected.

Aforementioned results have shown that teaching staffs are comparatively more prone to higher degree perceived reactions to Quality of Work Life than their supportive staffs i.e. non-teaching group especially from where the present sample has been drawn for the present piece of research work. Hence, the significance of difference between the groups has been found.

DISCUSSION:

Having presented the results obtained, it is important to point out that all the employees either teaching or non-teaching groups, both have shown quite favourable reactions towards their perceived reactions to Quality of Work Life. This is evident from the results obtained that they scored higher (above average score) on the Quality of Work Life scale.

The results as given in table-2 indicated that the teaching employees' Mean score is 196.73 with an S.D. of 28.75. This information clearly shows that the working teaching groups have significantly higher degree of Quality of Work Life as compared to supportive staff i.e. non-teaching group as they reported Mean value on Quality of Work Life i.e. 177.25 with an SD 20.38 especially from where the present sample has been drawn. Consequently, the difference between Teaching and non-teaching group of employees working in different universities of Bihar State such as L.N. Mithila University, Darbhanga, B. R. A. Bihar University, Muzaffarpur, B. N. Mandal University, Madhepura and Patna University, Patna India seems to be quite logical as socio-cultural living pattern of teaching group is being observed as moderately modernized according to their needs and demands of fast changing society which is, at present, based on hi- info-tech as Bihar Government as per UGC norms have launched several programmes for making congenial environment within academics to come up on international arena. Moreover, to meet the demands and to cater their needs, the teaching group of employees working in different universities of Bihar State continues to work to enhance their teaching and research career for the promotion of nation building at large in addition to their prime jobs as reported by teaching staffs during investigation. Hence, teaching group working in their respective state have shown higher degree of perceived quality of work life leading to best life satisfaction than their supportive staffs i.e. non-teaching group. They really deserve a lot of credit. That's why their services for the promotion of healthy society throughout the nation based on modern education can not be ignored.

Discussing the results obtained with regard to the non-teaching group of employees working in the same universities as mentioned above, it is important to point out that this group of employees has also shown positive but above moderate level of inclination towards perceived Quality of Work Life than their teaching group which can be observed from the table- 1 & 2. In obtaining such a discrepancy of results, it is substantial to throw light some of the observations, experienced by the present investigator, i.e. lack of organizational resources such as delay in salary, inadequate

amount of salary, political uncertainty prevailing in different universities of Bihar state regarding the policies, lack of proper care and cooperation from the side of authority in general and state government in particular and lack of other benefits, etc. these are basic reasons as have been observed by which non-teaching group especially in the universities of Bihar State and its constituent colleges are being affected. Non-teaching group also reported that they feel lack of social support and unhappiness of their family members due to inevitable delay in promotion and payment along with all perks and benefits, although, they are ready to contribute a lot to the betterment of higher education in all respect to uplift hygienic society.

In continuation to the above context, it is important to be mentioned here that to attain this sense of achievement without having any feeling of shyness non-teaching employees of universities of Bihar State willingly sacrifice leisure, family life, love and that comfortable social preservative, the conventions. Instead of these it seems, therefore, that non-teaching group reported positive reactions towards perceived Quality of Work Life especially from where the sample has been drawn. Really it shows whole mark of work environment in the Bihar state.

CONCLUSION:

On the basis of interpretations of the results the important conclusions are summed up below:

- Teaching and non-teaching employees working in different universities of Bihar State have been showing favourable inclination towards Quality of Work Life.
- Significance of difference has been found between Teaching and Non-teaching employees in the Bihar State in terms of over all Quality of Work Life.

- Teaching employees have been found comparatively more prone to higher degree of Quality of Work Life than non-teaching employees working in different universities of Bihar State.
- Observations have revealed the fact that there is a need to pay much more attention to the necessities of the non-teaching group working in different universities of Bihar State in particular and other employees in general such as adequate amount of salary, well-furnished housing facilities, promotional benefit, proper care and cooperation from concerned authorities and other perks and benefits as provided to the central government employees. This is only the way by which positive work ethics and greater sense of commitment in different universities and its constituent Colleges especially in Bihar State can be maintained without having any feeling of shyness, inferiority and loosing sense of esteem needs.

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